

Appendix

The results presented in this appendix are organised into five major sections:

- a) **Tool description:** for general information about the tool;
- b) **Tool functions:** for more detailed information about the tool;
- c) **Tool data:** for input and output data type information;
- d) **Tool users:** for information on the users of the tool (if existent);
- e) **Tool references:** bibliographic references about the tool for a deeper understanding.

The **tool description section** is a comprehensive resource, offering information about each tool. It includes details such as the source (CORDIS, WOS or Scopus, MOSAIC Internal Survey, Grey literature), tool name, a brief description, an online link, the level of development (Prototype, Under development, Operational), the type of developer (Public Administration, Academy/Research centre, Enterprise, Other), email contact, and the launching year of the tool and country of origin.

The **tool function section** delves deep into the details, comprehensively understanding each tool. It covers aspects such as the type of tool (Analysis, Simulation, Stakeholder Engagement, Land use modelling, Scenario modelling, Interaction and visualisation), policy sector (Governance, Spatial planning, Forestry, Agriculture, Rural areas, Protected areas management, Biodiversity, Environment, Climate, Energy, Multiple), main land use domain (Forest Management, Rural Land Development, Natural Resource Management, Ecology, Biodiversity and Conservation, Green Infrastructure, Renewable Energy, Energy Landscapes, Agricultural/Forestry Decision Support Systems, Water Management, Mixed Land Uses), the presence of spatially explicit output, and the scale of tool development (EU, National, Regional, Local).

The **tool data section** includes information about the input and output data used in each tool, namely, general input data type (Qualitative, Quantitative, Both), Detailed input data type (Statistics, Spatial information, Expert knowledge, Field survey data, Dataset), Output data type (Map, Graphics, Texts, Aggregated data), Output timeframe (current, short-medium term, long term).

The **tool user section** covers some information about the users of each tool, whenever the information is available, namely the type of users (Citizens, Academy, Policy makers, Land Managers, All, Others) and the time required to use or learn to use the tool (low, medium or high).

The last section – **tool reference** – gathers the bibliographic references about the tool for a deeper understanding.

		Tool DESCRIPTION										Tool FUNCTIONS							Tool DATA		Tool REFERENCES	
Database of Origin/Information Source	ID	Tool name	Description	Online link	Level of development	Developer/Publisher	Type of Developer	Launching Year	Country of origin	Type of Tool	Policy sector	Main Land Use Domain	Spatially explicit output	Scale	General input data type	Detailed input data type	Output data type	Output timeframe	Users	Type of end-users	Time requirement	
Name	No.	Name	75 characters	Link	Operational	Name	Public Administration Academy/Research center Enterprise Other	YYYY		Analysis Simulation Stakeholder Engagement Land use modelling Scenario modelling Interaction and visualization	Protected areas management	Forest Management Rural Land Development Natural Resource Management Ecology, Biodiversity and Conservation Green Infrastructure Renewable Energy Landscapes Agricultural/Forestry Decision Support Systems Water Management Mixed Land Uses	Yes, No	EU National Regional Local	Qualitative Quantitative Both	Spatial information Expert knowledge Field survey data Dataset	Map Graphics Texts Aggregated data	Current Short-medium term Long term	Number	Citizens Academy Policymakers Land Managers All Others	Low Medium High	Bibliography or web-site
	1	CO-IMPACT	Developed within the Connecting Nature Project, CO-IMPACT is a decision-support tool allowing officers and cities to create impact assessment plans for their NBS/projects. The main objective is to make the process of building a baseline and impact assessment plan straight forward and simple for anyone who wishes to do so, with the final report providing advice around suitable methodologies based on scale and project characteristics	https://co-impact.app/	Operational	University of Coruña	Academy/Research Center	2021	EU Consortium (Spain Coordinator)	Analysis	Multiple	Green Infrastructure	no	Local	Qualitative, Expert knowledge	Texts	Current	no data	All	Low	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/730222	
	2	ECOPotential view	ECOPotential is a project funded by the European Union, focused on research and monitoring of protected ecosystems. This project uses satellite data and other Earth observation technologies to analyze and model ecosystem dynamics, with the aim of supporting the conservation and sustainable management of protected areas.	https://maps.ecopotential-project.eu/	Operational	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE; UNIVERSITA DEL SALENTO; CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	Academy/Research Center	2015	EU Consortium (United Kingdom Coordinator)	Interaction and visualization	Protected areas management	Mixed Land Uses	yes	EU, national and regional	Qualitative, Expert knowledge	Map	Current	no data	Land managers	Medium	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/641762	
	3	ERA-PLANET	European Union-funded research program that aims to coordinate and integrate environmental observation infrastructure in Europe. This program is part of the Horizon 2020 initiative and involves several countries and research institutions.	http://www.era-planet.eu/index.php	Operational		Academy/Research Center	2015	EU Consortium (Italy coordinator)	Stakeholder Engagement	Environment	Mixed Land Uses	no	EU and national	Qualitative,	Texts	Current	no data	Land managers	Medium	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/689443	
	4	GROW	The GROW Observatory will create a sustainable citizen platform and community to generate, share and utilise information on land, soil and water resource at a resolution hitherto not previously considered. The vision is to underpin smart and sustainable custodianship of land and soil, whilst meeting the demands of food production, and to answer a long-standing challenge for space science, namely the validation of soil moisture detection from satellites.	https://iasa.ac.at/models-tools-data/grow-observatory-app	Operational	UNIVERSITY OF DUNDEE	Academy/Research Center	2016	EU Consortium (United Kingdom Coordinator)	Interaction and visualization	Multiple	Mixed Land Uses	yes	National and regional	Both	Spatial information	Aggregated data	Current	7.8M People reached	Citizens	Low	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/690199
	5	GROW GREEN	GROW GREEN will provide the platform for a step change in the way that NBS are embedded in the long-term planning, development, operation and management of cities around the world. The NBS Business Models search engine offers a first orientation and inspiration to decision-makers on the type of interventions using Natural Based Solutions may be most appropriate for them, considering the specific problems they want to solve in their cities or companies, or the objectives they intend to achieve.	https://growgreenproject.eu/	Operational	MANCHESTER CITY COUNCIL	Public administration	2017	EU Consortium (United Kingdom Coordinator)	Interaction and visualization	Environment	Green Infrastructure	no	Local	Quantitative	Dataset	Aggregated data	Current	no data	All	Low	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/730283
CORDIS (TOT 18)	6	ISQAPER	Knowledge regarding the complex interplay between agricultural land use and management and soil quality and function is fragmented and incomplete, in particular with regard to underlying principles and regulating mechanisms. The main aim of ISQAPER is to develop an interactive soil quality assessment tool (SQAPP) for agricultural land users that integrates newly derived process understanding and accounts for the impact of agricultural land use and management on soil properties and functions, and related ecosystem services. Currently within the EU's Earth Observation (EO) monitoring framework, there is a need for low-cost methods for acquiring high quality in-situ data to create accurate and well-validated environmental monitoring products. The aim of the LandSense project is to build a far reaching citizen observatory for Land Use and Land Cover (LULC) monitoring that will also function as a technology innovation marketplace.	Home (isqaper-project.eu)	Operational	WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY	Academy/Research Center	2015	EU Consortium (Spain Coordinator)	Interaction and visualization	Agriculture	Agricultural/Forestry Decision Support Systems	yes	Local	Both	Spatial information	Aggregated data	Current	11918	All	Low	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/635750
	7	LANDSENSE	MySustainableForest aims at developing a pre-commercial service platform for forest stakeholders, compliant with open and standard interfaces, which integrates Earth Observation data into the forest stakeholders' decision making processes and operations.	https://mysustainableforest.com/project-description/	Operational	GMV Aerospace and Defence S.A.U.	Enterprise	2018	EU Consortium (Spain Coordinator)	Land Use modelling	Forestry	Forest Management	yes	EU and national	Both	Spatial information	Aggregated data	Current	no data	All	Medium	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/776045
	9	NAIAD	Focus on assessing and demonstrating the insurance value of nature. NAIAD's primary objective is to develop and test nature-based solutions (NBS) to reduce water-related risks, such as floods and droughts, and demonstrate how these ecological services can be integrated into risk management and insurance strategies.	https://naiad2020.eu/	Operational	ICATALIST	Academy/Research Center	2016	EU Consortium (Spain coordinator)	Stakeholder Engagement	Multiple	Natural Resource Management	yes	Regional	Qualitative, Spatial information	Texts	Current	no data	Policy makers	Low	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/730497	
	10	NATURVATION	Focuses on promoting nature-based solutions (NBS) in urban environments to address social, environmental and economic challenges.	https://naturvation-navigator.com/	Operational	Durham University	Academy/Research Center	2017	EU Consortium (United Kingdom coordinator)	Analysis	Multiple	Mixed Land Uses	no	EU, national and regional	Qualitative,	Texts	Current	no data	Policy makers	Low	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/730243	
	11	NBS Simulation Visualization Tool	The Nature-Based Solutions Simulation Visualization Tool (NBS) is an advanced platform intended to support the implementation of nature-based solutions (NBS) to address urban environmental challenges such as climate change, water management and loss of biodiversity. This tool allows users to visualize and analyze the impacts of NBS in urban settings, facilitating informed decision-making by urban planners, engineers and policymakers.	https://unlab.eng.it/nbsvt_v4/home.jsp?city=genova&scale=local&year=2030&indicator=default&impact=default&scenario=00&prevision=10	Operational	Smith School of Environment and Enterprise	Enterprise	2017	EU Consortium (Italy Coordinator)	Simulation	Multiple	Ecology, Biodiversity and Conservation	yes	Local	Qualitative, Spatial information	Map	Short-medium term	no data	All	Medium	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/730052	
	12	OPERANDUM	Severe hydro-meteorological phenomena are having a high impact in European territories and are of global concern. The science behind these phenomena is complex and advancement in knowledge proceeds with progress in data acquisition and forecasting useful for real-scenario interventions	OPERANDUM OPEN-air lab/LabForNature-based-solutions-to-Manage-hydro-meteo-risks-(operandum-project.eu)	Operational	ALMA MATER STUDIUM - UNIVERSITA DI BOLOGNA	Academy/Research Center	2018	EU Consortium (Italy Coordinator)	Analysis	Climate	Mixed Land Uses	no	National, regional and local	Both	Expert knowledge	Texts	Current	no data	All	Low	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/776848
	13	RE CARE	The RE CARE project is a European initiative focused on the prevention and remediation of soil degradation in Europe. The aim of the Stakeholders Platforms is to enable interaction between all those people who are interested in the RE CARE project activities in a particular Case Study area.	https://www.recare-hub.eu/stakeholder-platforms	Operational	Wageningen University	Academy/Research Center	2013	EU Consortium (Netherlands Coordinator)	Stakeholder Engagement	Agriculture	Agricultural/Forestry Decision Support Systems	yes	EU and national	Both	Spatial information	Texts	Current	no data	All	Low	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/603498

MOSAIC Internal Survey (TOT 15)	14	RUBIZMO	Rural entrepreneurs in the bioeconomy find it difficult to access funding, skilled employees and innovation support networks. The EU-funded RUBIZMO project will identify innovative business models (developed or identified in projects under the Seventh Framework Programme, Horizon 2020, Interreg, Central Europe, etc.) with significant potential to support modernisation and sustainable growth in rural economies. These will also be relevant to the food sector, bio-based value chains and ecosystem services. The selection and classification of models will be deployed for the creation of a virtual library of business cases, the drafting of guidelines for public authorities and policymakers, a cooperation toolkit for efficient networking and a transformation support tool for novice entrepreneurs.	https://rubizmo.eu/e-learning	Operational	RISE RESEARCH INSTITUTES OF SWEDEN AB	Academy/Research Center	2018	EU Consortium (Sweden Coordinator)	Interaction and visualization	Rural Development	Rural Land Development	no	Regional	Qualitative, Expert knowledge	Aggregated data	Current	no data	Land managers	Low	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/73621	
	15	SCENT	SCENT - Smart Toolbox for Engaging Citizens into a People-Centric Observation Web - The project designed, developed and implemented a people-centric observation web, formulated on the basis of using low-cost, portable sensors and innovative applications. The SCENT toolbox offers various capabilities involving crowdsourcing and serious gaming mechanisms towards enabling, incentivising and increasing the involvement of citizens as individuals and/or citizen groups/associations in the process of environmental monitoring. By using their smartphones and portable sensors, citizens can take images of land cover / land use while walking around in their city or the countryside, report events that may affect floods (e.g. river obstacles) and measure water level, flow velocity and soil moisture, without complex or bulky equipment. They are doing this in a playful manner, through a game of catching animated animals in their surroundings and collecting points.	https://scent-project.eu/	Operational	National Technical University of Athens	Academy/Research Center	2016	EU Consortium (Greece Coordinator)	Analysis	Environment	Natural Resource Management	yes	Local	Both	Spatial information	Aggregated data	Long term	no data	All	Medium	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/688930
	16	SIMNEXUS	SIMNEXUS has developed a Serious Game. The Serious Game is a computer game that aids learning about the Nexus by helping users to understand and explore the interactions between water, energy, land and food resources management under a climate change context, divides the problem into manageable interventions, and allows participants to learn by doing. The ultimate goal of game development is to create a fun and interactive capacity-building tool to be used in research, educational settings and management.	https://seriousgame.sim4nexus.eu/sim4nexus-MainPage.html?id=250e65f5-a592-4985-abfc-38e8099350e5#world_map	Operational	Wageningen University & Research (WUR)	Academy/Research Center	2016	EU Consortium (Netherlands Coordinator)	Interaction and visualization	Multiple	Mixed Land Uses	yes	EU and national	Qualitative, Spatial information	Map	Current	no data	Policy makers	Low	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/689150	
	17	SmartCulTour	The SmartCulTour Game is an integral part of a set of intervention toolkits for the six SmartCulTour Living Labs. With its playful approach to policy making, the game aims to engage stakeholders to learn about cultural tourism and interventions to make cultural tourism more sustainable for communities, the environment, and creative businesses.	http://www.smartcultour.eu/smartcultour-platform/	Operational	Breda University of Applied Sciences	Academy/Research Center	2023	EU Consortium (Netherlands Coordinator)	Stakeholder Engagement	Governance	Mixed Land Uses	no	Regional	Qualitative, Expert knowledge	Aggregated data	Current	no data	All	Low	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/870708	
	18	URBAN GreenUP	Urban GreenUp objective is the development, application and replication of Renaturing Urban Plans in a number of European and Non-European partner cities with the aim to mitigate the effects of climate change	https://www.cartif.es/en/urban-greenup-en/	Operational	CARTIF Technology Centre	Academy/Research Center	2017	EU Consortium (Netherlands Coordinator)	Stakeholder Engagement	Environment	Mixed Land Uses	yes	Regional and local	Both	Spatial information	Texts		no data	All	Medium	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/730426
	19	CRAFTY	Agent-based modelling framework for application primarily at large spatial scales (national-continental), in the land system. Model applications are usually cross-sectoral and exploratory, analysing land system dynamics under global change. As an agent-based framework, a focus is on the decision-making processes of land managers, and their role in social-ecological systems.	https://landchange.earth.CRAFTY	Operational	Various	Academy/Research Center	2014	UK/Germany	Simulation;Land Use modelling;Scenario modelling	Forestry;Agriculture;Protected areas management;Biodiversity;Environment; Climate	Forest Management;Ecology, Biodiversity and Conservation;Renewable Energy;Mixed Land Uses	yes	Europe;National	Both	Statistics;Spatial information; Expert knowledge;Field survey data;Dataset	Aggregated data	Long term	no data	Academy	Medium	collected at
	20	Dynamic Energy Atlas	The Dynamic Energy Atlas enables to address the spatial dimension of the energy system in its full complexity. It supports mapping, monitoring, trend and scenario analysis in a quest for (new) suitable locations for energy production taking into consideration energy demand as well as technological, spatial planning land use and environmental constraints and concerns. The tool tackles possible locations for PV, residual heat exchange, wind turbines, hydropower, geothermal energy, biomass energy installations, rithermia, ...	http://dx.doi.org/10.4229/EUPVS-EC20202020-7DO.9.1	Operational	VITO	Academy/Research Center	2015	Belgium	Analysis;Simulation;Scenario modelling;Interaction and visualization	Spatial planning;Energy	Renewable Energy;Energy Landscapes	yes	National;Regional	Quantitative	Statistics;Spatial information; Expert knowledge; Dataset	Spatially explicit;Map;Graphics;Aggregated data	Current;Short-term;Long term	no data	Policy makers	Medium	Meuris, M., Voroshazi, E., Cathoor, F., Meinke-Hubeny, F., Uljee, I., Lemmens, J., Horváth, L.T., Duchêne, F., Clymans, W., & Schils, A. (2020). Towards Country Scale Photovoltaic Energy Yield Modelling.
	21	Swiss SolarWind Explorer	The Swiss SolarWind Explorer (SSWE) web tool was developed with the aim of identifying areas in Switzerland that are suitable for solar and wind energy plants and cause as few conflicts of objectives as possible. The tool is aimed at spatial planners in cantons and municipalities, energy companies, teachers, researchers and interested private individuals. It can help to make a complex and often abstract topic understandable and to support it with quantitative data. In this way, the development of sustainable solutions for solar and wind power plants should be supported.	https://swiss-solarwind-explorer.vl.ethz.ch/	Operational	ETH Zurich / Chair Planning of Landscapes and Urban Systems	Academy/Research Center	2025	Switzerland	Simulation Stakeholder Engagement Scenario modelling Interaction and visualization	Spatial planning Climate Energy Multiple	Rural Land Development;Ecology, Biodiversity and Conservation;Renewable Energy;Energy Landscapes	yes	National;Regional;Local	Qualitative	Spatial information Dataset	Map	Long term	no data	All	Medium	https://swiss-solarwind-explorer.ethz.ch/
	22	EPIC WebGIS	EPIC WebGIS is an interactive spatial data infrastructure, which provides georeferenced cartography from national to municipal scale, using data visualization tools. It can be seen as a landscape planning instrument, offering immediate access to several available themes concerning ecosystems, ecological network and ecological land suitability.	http://epic-webgis-portugal.iss.ulisboa.pt/	Operational	LEAF/ISA	Academy/Research Center	2013	Portugal	Interaction and visualization	Spatial planning	Mixed Land Uses	Yes	National, regional and local	Both	Spatial information	Map	Current	no data	All	Low	Magalhães, M.R., Pena, S.B., Müller, A., Cunha, N.S., Silva, J.S., Cardoso, A.S., Barata, L.T., Franco, L., 2018. EPIC WebGIS - A partilha de conhecimento como ferramenta de integração da paisagem nas políticas de ordenamento do território. Revista Cartográfica Nº 96. Instituto Panamericano de Geografia e História. https://doi.org/10.35424/rcarto.i96.193 (ISSN 0080-2085 (Print) 2663-3981 (Online))
	23	IMPACT tool of the Flemish Climate portal	This tool allow people to map what the local impact will be of climate change. It is a map of Flanders where people can zoom in or out. To make it simple the tool shows the results of the climate scenario with high impact (statistically as likely as any other scenario and aligning with current emissions). The tool shows the impact on various challenges: heat, drought, groundwater stress, sea level rise, fluvial floods, pluvial floods. The tool also shows you a rough estimate of the vulnerability based on parameters such as local housing and industry.	https://impacttool.toepassingen.vmm.vlaanderen.be/2	Operational	Flanders Environment Agency (VMM)	Developed by academia for public administration. Now maintained by the administration.	2018	Belgium (only the northern part: Flanders)	Scenario modelling	Spatial planning;Climate	Green Infrastructure;Water Management	yes	Regional	Quantitative	Statistics;Dataset;Makes use of statistical modelling of possible future climates + existing geodatasets of Flanders	Map	Long term	no data	Policy makers; Land managers	Low	https://vmm.vlaanderen.be/publicaties/klimaatportal-vlaanderen (in Dutch)
	24	INCA tool	The INCA Tool is a QGIS plugin to support the calculation of ecosystem services accounts. The methodology implemented in the tool is aligned with the proposed European legislation on ecosystem accounts. Additionally, the tool supports the calculation of two voluntary accounts in line with the global standard of the System of Environmental-Economic Accounts (SEEA EA).	https://ecosystem-accounts.jrc.ec.europa.eu/inca-tool https://ecosystem-accounts.jrc.ec.europa.eu/	Operational	Research Centre and the European Environment Agency VITO	Academy/Research Center	2023	EU	Analysis	Governance;Economics, accounting	Mixed Land Uses;All land	yes	Europe	Quantitative	Statistics	Aggregated data	Current	no data	Policy makers	Medium	Vallecillo, S., La Notte, A., Ferrini, S., & Maes, J. (2019). How ecosystem services are changing: An accounting application at the EU level. Ecosystem Services, 40, 101044. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2019.101044

25	InVEST®	Assessment of ecosystem services spatially	https://naturalcapitalproject.stanford.edu/software/invest	Operational	Stanford university, Natural Capital Project	Academy/Research Center	2008	USA	Analysis;Simulation;Interaction and visualization	Spatial planning;Forestry;Agriculture;Rural Development;Protected areas management;Biodiversity	Forest Management;Rural Land Development;Ecology, Biodiversity and Conservation;Mixed Land Uses	yes	Europe;National;Regional;Local	Quantitative	Spatial information; Expert knowledge;Field survey data;Dataset	Spatially explicit;Map;Graphics;Aggregated data	Current;Short-medium term;Long term	no data	All	Medium	https://naturalcapitalproject.stanford.edu/software/invest
26	Land-use Planner	The Land-use Planner is a freely accessible tool for anyone interested in participatory land-use planning. It allows to compare different land-use scenarios. The tool supports countries in implementing responsible and participatory land-use planning. This is done through multi-criteria analysis to better balance economic interests with social inclusion and environmental protection. The tool can also be used to develop, check and refine investment plans and present them to stakeholders. It can act as a negotiation to involve competing stakeholders in a planning process.	https://landuseplanner.org/	Operational	European Forest Institute	Academy/Research Center	2023	Finland	Analysis;Simulation;Stakeholder Engagement;Land Use modelling;Scenario modelling;Interaction and visualization	Governance;Spatial planning;Forestry;Agriculture;Rural Development;Biodiversity;Environment	Forest Management;Rural Land Development;Ecology, Biodiversity and Conservation;Agricultural/Forestry Decision Support Systems	yes	National;Regional;Local	Quantitative	Statistics;Expert knowledge;Dataset	Graphics;Texts;Aggregated data	Short-medium term;Long term	no data	Policy makers; Land managers	Medium	Not available
27	Nature value explorer	Belgian decision support tool. Free webbased tool which estimates the impact of land use change on the delivery of ecosystem services. Rural and urban version. The urban version works similar as the rural one but it is more to map the benefits of green-blue measure in the city. The rural tool is mostly based on statistical functions calculating biophysical terms of ecosystem services delivery (e.g. ton C, kg N, m ³ infiltration, no of visits...). There is also a monetary value given to that when possible. Urban tool is more on key numbers per green or blue measure.	https://www.natuurwaardeverkenner.be/	Operational	VITO	Academy/Research Center	2013	Belgium	Analysis;Interaction and visualization;assessment	Spatial planning;Forestry;Agriculture;Rural Development;Protected areas management;Climate	Forest Management;Rural Land Development;Natural Resource Management;Green Infrastructure;Mixed Land Uses	yes	National	Both	Spatial information	Aggregated data	Current;Short-medium term	no data	Academy;Policy makers; Land managers	Low	Steven Broekx, Inge Liekens, Wim Peelaerts, Leo De Nocker, Dries Landuyt, Jan Staes, Patrick Meire, Marije Schaafsma, Wouter Van Reeth, Olivier Van den Kerckhove, Tanya Cerulus, A web application to support the quantification and valuation of ecosystem services, Environmental Impact Assessment Review, Volume 40, 2013, Pages 65-74, ISSN 0195-9255, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2013.01.003
28	NEXUS Learn	Transition tools for co-creation which can be used in many different transition processes, land use decision making being just one of them.	https://coda.io/@vito/nexuslearn/transition-tools-10	Operational	NEXUS team at VITO	Academy/Research Center	2022	Belgium	Stakeholder Engagement;Interaction and visualization	Governance;the tools can be applied to any sector	applicable to many situations	yes	Europe;National;Regional;Local	Qualitative	Spatial information; Expert knowledge;Field survey data;stakeholder input through co-creation	Aggregated data	Current;Short-medium term;Long term	no data	All	Medium	Not available
29	PANDORA A 3.0 plugin	The PANDORA 3.0 model, developed as a QGIS plugin and illustrated here with a study case, is the first free, open-source tool for an integrated evaluation of ecosystem services related to landscape connectivity for biodiversity conservation purposes in urban contexts.	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2017.05.016	Operational	Francesco Geri	Public administration	2017	Italia	Analysis;Simulation	Spatial planning	Green Infrastructure	yes	National	Qualitative	Dataset	Aggregated data	Current	no data	Land managers	High	Pelorusso, R., Gobattoni, F., Geri, F., Leone, A. PANDORA 3.0 plugin: A new biodiversity ecosystem service assessment tool for urban green infrastructure connectivity planning, Ecosystem Services, Volume 26, Part B, 2017, Pages 476-482, ISSN 2212-0416, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2017.05.016
30	Reinvent your street	This tool is developed for people to get inspired. With playful research AI regenerates street view and aims to show what streets could also look like.	https://dutchcyclinglifestyle.com/	Operational	NL Netherlands	Other	No data	Netherlands	Simulation;Stakeholder Engagement;Interaction and visualization	Spatial planning	Mixed Land Uses;Urban	no	Local	Both	Spatial information	Aggregated data	Current	no data	Citizens; Policy makers	Low	Not available
31	RuimteModel Vlaanderen / Geodynamix	Land use model to simulate possible future land use at a medium to high resolution.	https://mitpress.mit.edu/9780262029568/modeling-cities-and-regions-as-complex-systems/	Operational	VITO	Academy/Research Center	2007	Belgium	Analysis;Simulation;Land Use modelling;Scenario modelling	Spatial planning;Forestry;Agriculture	Mixed Land Uses	yes	Regional	Quantitative	Expert knowledge	Map	Current	no data	Policy makers	High	White, R., Engelen, G. and Ujse, I., 2015. Modeling Cities and Regions as Complex Systems From Theory to Planning Applications. ISBN: 9780262029568
32	UNBiodiversity Lab	UN Biodiversity Lab is a free, open-source environment that provides decision makers with the best available spatial data to put nature at the center of sustainable development. The user can explore data collections and create their own workspace (secure collaborative work environment to upload national data). 'Maps of hope' are created via national partnerships to identify where nature-based actions can safeguard essential life support areas to maintain key biodiversity and ecosystem services. Success stories and impact stories can be submitted to share online.	https://unbiodiversitylab.org/en/	Operational	Partnership of UNDP, UNEP, UNEP-WCMC, CBD Secretariat	United Nations	2018	UN	Interaction and visualization	Governance;Spatial planning;Biodiversity;Environment	Ecology, Biodiversity and Conservation	yes	Europe;National;Regional	Quantitative	Spatial information; Dataset	Map	Current	no data	Policy makers; Land managers	Low	https://unbiodiversitylab.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/UNBL-2022-Annual-Report-FNL.pdf
33	Watch-R-Grow	WatchITgrow is an online platform to support growers to monitor arable crops and vegetables in view of sustainably increasing yields, both qualitatively and quantitatively. WatchITgrow uses various types of data starting with satellite data combined with e.g. weather data, soil data, IoT data and field data provided by the grower. These data are combined using new technologies such as big data analytics and machine learning to provide growers with more timely and personalized advice. WiG delivers currently: (a) objective and up-to-date crop-related data, (b) a clear overview of the status of the crops, (c) enabling the assessment to take specific and timely actions, (d) reduce potential production losses, (e) document the sustainable production, (f) collect and manage the farm data securely and digitally and (g) provide an automated damage assessment workflow for the agro insurance industry (e.g. KBC).	https://blog.vito.be/remotesensing/watchitgrow-connects	Operational	VITO	Academy/Research Center	2018	Belgium	Analysis;Simulation;Stakeholder Engagement;Land Use modelling;Scenario modelling;Interaction and visualization	Governance;Agriculture;Rural Development;Protected areas management;Biodiversity;Environment; Climate	Rural Land Development;Natural Resource Management;Ecology, Biodiversity and Conservation;Agricultural/Forestry Decision Support Systems	yes	Regional	Both	Statistics;Spatial information; Expert knowledge;Field survey data;Dataset; remote sensing (satellite and airborne derived)	Spatially explicit;Map	Short-medium term	no data	All	Medium	https://blog.vito.be/remotesensing/watchitgrow-connects
34	LandSFAC TS	LANDscape Scale Functional Allocation of Crops Temporally and Spatially Visualisations employed texture-based rendering rather than full photo-realistic rendering to facilitate interactivity and this provided additional scope for audiences to explore multiple future scenarios compared to the present landscape. Interactive voting in a virtual landscape theatre suggested preferences for visual diversity, good stewardship and perceived naturalness that should be considered in developing planned responses to change.	https://www.hutton.ac.uk/departments/landfacts-downloads/	Operational	Hutton University	Academy/Research Center	2015	United Kingdom	Interaction and visualization	Spatial planning	Mixed Land Uses	yes	Local	Both	Dataset	Aggregated data	Short-medium term	no data	All	Medium	Wang, C., Miller, D., Brown, I., Jiang, Y., & Castellazzi, M. (2016). Visualisation techniques to support public interpretation of future climate change and land-use choices: A case study from N-E Scotland. International Journal of Digital Earth, 9(6), 586-605. https://doi.org/10.1080/17538947.2015.1111949
35	MPMAS	MPMAS is a software package for simulating land use change in agriculture and forestry. It combines economic models of farm household decision-making with a range of biophysical models simulating production response to changes in water supply and soil nutrients. MPMAS is part of a family of models called multi-agent systems models of land-use/cover change (MAS/LUCC).	https://mp-mas.uni-hohenheim.de/	Operational	Hohenheim University	Academy/Research Center	2011	Germany	Simulation	Agriculture	Agricultural/Forestry Decision Support Systems	yes	Regional and local	Both	Dataset	Aggregated data	Short-medium term	no data	Academy	High	Mössinger, J., Troost, C., & Berger, T. (2022). Bridging the gap between models and users: A lightweight mobile interface for optimized farming decisions in interactive modeling sessions. Agricultural Systems, 195, 103315. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2021.103315

Grey literature (TOT 11)	36	P@stor-all	P@stor-all is a platform co-designed with pastoral breeders allowing you to: gather heterogeneous data on the use of rangelands by herds analyze them, cross-reference them and put them into perspective to offer breeders, according to their needs and questions, "packages of information" to help them understand their system and make decisions. To do this, the platform is divided into two spaces: a private space intended for the analysis and interpretation of GPS data and a public space intended for the dissemination of resources and knowledge sharing.	https://pastorall.supaagro.inrae.fr/	Operational	L'institut Agro Montpellier	Academy/Research Center	2024	France	Analysis	Agriculture	Agricultural/Forestry Decision Support Systems	yes	Local	Both	Spatial information	Aggregated data	Current	no data	Land managers	Medium	Kalenga Tshingomba, U., Djibo, B., Sautot, L., Teisseire, M., & Jouven, M. (2022). A spatialised information system to support decisions regarding grazing management in mountainous and Mediterranean rangelands. <i>Computers and Electronics in Agriculture</i> , 198, 107100. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compag.2022.107100
	37	ZONATION	Zonation is a freely available decision support software tool for ecologically based land use planning including applications in spatial conservation planning and ecological impact avoidance.	https://zonationteam.github.io/Zonation5/	Operational	University of Helsinki	Academy/Research Center	2003	Finland	Land Use modelling	Multiple	Ecology, Biodiversity and Conservation	yes	National, regional and local	Both	Spatial information	Spatially explicit;Map	Short-medium term	no data	Academy	Medium	Moilanen, A., Lehtinen, P., Kohonen, I., Jalankari, J., Virtanen, E. A., & Kujala, H. (2022). Novel methods for spatial prioritization with applications in conservation, land use planning and ecological impact avoidance. <i>Methods in Ecology and Evolution</i> , 13(5), 1062–1072. https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.13819
	38	AKIS PORTUGAL	National Agricultural Development and Innovation System which brings together all the actors of the agricultural and floral sectors in the modernization of rural areas, promotion and implementation of development, innovation and digitalization in agriculture and rural areas.	https://akisportugal.pt/	Operational	Rede Rural (CAP National Network, under the Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development - DGADR).	Other	2020	Portugal	Stakeholder Engagement	Agriculture	Agricultural/Forestry Decision Support Systems	no	National	Both	Expert knowledge	Aggregated data	Current	no data	All	Low	Rui Almeida e Francisca Viveiros. 2020. AKIS and advisory services in Portugal. Report for the AKIS inventory (Task 1.2) of the i2connect project. (Project funded under the Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement number 863039)
	39	C.A.F.E (Carbon, Aqua, Fire & Eco-resilience)	This tool determines the optimum silvicultural activities to manage multiple products, goods and services such as biomass production, carbon sequestration, fire risk, water provisioning, climatic resilience or biodiversity, which are simultaneously quantified in time and space for a selected solution.	https://www.resilientforest.eu/dss-tool/ ; https://www.resilientforest.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/Manual_eng_Version1.pdf	Operational	Life Resilient Forest	Academy/Research Center	2023	Germany, Portugal and Spain	Interaction and visualization	Forestry	Agricultural/Forestry Decision Support Systems	yes	Local	Both	Dataset	Map	Current	no data	Land managers	Medium	https://www.resilientforest.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/DSS-TOOL-.pdf
	40	ClimateMatch	Compare a site's future climate to current locations in Europe.	https://climatematch.org.uk/	Operational	Nick Synes	Academy/Research Center	2022	United Kingdom	Simulation	Climate	Natural Resource Management	yes	National, regional and local	Both	Expert knowledge	Aggregated data	Current	no data	All	Low	Broadmeadow, M. S. J., Ray, D., & Samuel, C. J. A. (2005). Climate change and the future for broadleaved tree species in Britain. <i>Forestry: An International Journal of Forest Research</i> , 78(2), 145–161. https://doi.org/10.1093/forestry/cpi014
	41	CropSAT	CropSAT is a tool to survey your field from above. Maps of the biomass variation within the field is calculated from satellite imagery. You can use the variation maps to see how your crop develops during the season and to control your N-application based on crop N need. CropSAT is an interactive application and allows you to easily create variation maps from the satellite imagery vegetation index. The maps can be downloaded and used for variable rate nitrogen application. CropSAT is, simply put, a crop sensing system for everybody.	https://cropsat.com/	Operational	Department of Soil and Environment, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences	Academy/Research Center	2015	Sweden	Analysis	Agriculture	Ecology, Biodiversity and Conservation	yes	Local	Qualitative, Spatial information	Aggregated data	Current	no data	All	Low	Alshihabi, O., Piikki, K., & Söderström, M. (2020). CropSAT – A Decision Support System for Practical Use of Satellite Images in Precision Agriculture. In A. El Moussati, K. Kpalma, M. Ghaouth Belkassi, M. Saber, & S. Guégan (Eds.), <i>Advances in Smart Technologies Applications and Case Studies</i> (pp. 415–421). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-53187-4_45	
	42	E-Planner	E-Planner is a free tool developed by UKCEH to help farmers and other land managers identify the most suitable places for different environmental management actions via easy to use, interactive maps. E-Planner uses environmental datasets to build GB-coverage maps of the relative suitability of land for different environmental opportunities. Each opportunity has a range of associated potential management actions, depending on the farming system and local context, but with relative suitability driven by similar factors	https://e-planner.ceh.ac.uk	Operational	UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology (UKCEH)	Academy/Research Center	2020	United Kingdom	Interaction and visualization	Agriculture	Agricultural/Forestry Decision Support Systems	yes	National, regional and local	Both	Spatial information	Aggregated data	Current	no data	All	Low	Redhead, J. W., Burkmar, R., Brown, M., & Pywell, R. F. (2022). E-Planner: A web-based tool for planning environmental enhancement on British agricultural land. <i>Environmental Modelling & Software</i> , 155, 105437. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2022.105437
	43	Global Forest Watch	Global Forest Watch is an open-source web application to monitor global forests in near real-time. The tool provides a map and dashboard to empower users to better protect forests. The user can explore global and local datasets to learn about conservation, land use, forest communities and more. The map allows to see deforestation over time and you have access to global and country stats to analyze forest change and trends.	https://www.globalforestwatch.org/	Operational	World Resources Institute (WRI)	Other	1997	USA	Interaction and visualization	Multiple	Mixed Land Uses	yes	EU, national and regional	Qualitative, Expert knowledge	Aggregated data	Current	no data	All	Low	Estoque, R. C., Johnson, B. A., Dasgupta, R., Gao, Y., Matsuura, T., Toma, T., Hirata, Y., & Lasco, R. D. (2022). Rethinking forest monitoring for more meaningful global forest landscape change assessments. <i>Journal of Environmental Management</i> , 317, 115478. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.115478	
	44	Land App	Tool to bring together data, people, knowledge and incentives in a modern and accessible online platform to collectively move towards smarter land use and start to address the major issues of our time. Partnering with leading conservation organisations, food retailers, land management professionals and government bodies, we equip our users with the digital tools they need to navigate the agricultural transition and unlock a sustainable future.	https://thelandapp.com/about-us/	Operational	DIGITALLAN DSOLUTIONS LTD, 2024	Other	2023	United Kingdom	Interaction and visualization	Protected areas management	Ecology, Biodiversity and Conservation	yes	Local	Both	Spatial information	Aggregated data	Current	no data	Land managers	Low	Not available
	45	LANDSUPPORT	The LANDSUPPORT project aims at developing a web-based completely free, open-access GeoSpatial Decision Support System (S-DSS) devoted to: support sustainable agriculture and forestry; evaluate trade-off between land uses; contribute to the development and implementation of land use policies in Europe.	https://www.landsupport.eu/	Operational	CRISP – UNIVERSITÀ DI NAPOLI FEDERICO II	Academy/Research Center	2018	Italy, Austria, Hungary, Germany, Spain, France, Belgium, Slovenia, Malaysia and Tunisia	Interaction and visualization	Multiple	Agricultural/Forestry Decision Support Systems	yes	EU, national and regional	Qualitative, Spatial information	Map	Current	no data	All	Medium	Terribile, F., Acutis, M., Agrillo, A., Anzalone, E., Azam-Ali, S., Banchen, M., Baumann, P., Birli, B., Bonfante, A., Botta, M., Cavaliere, F., Colandrea, M., D'Antonio, A., de Mascellis, R., de Michele, C., de Paoli, G., Monica, C. della, di Legnino, M., Ferlan, M., ... Basile, A. (2023). The LANDSUPPORT geospatial decision support system (S-DSS) vision: Operational tools to implement sustainability policies in land planning and management. <i>Land Degradation & Development</i> . https://doi.org/10.1002/LDR.4954	
46	Land-use Finance Tool	The Land-use Finance Tool is a diagnostic tool that enables a quantitative and qualitative analysis of the alignment of public and private spending with climate and forest objectives.	https://landusefinance.org/	Operational	European Forest Institute, Climate Policy Initiative	Academy/Research Center	2018	United kingdom	Analysis	Forestry	Forest Management	no	National	Both	Expert knowledge	Texts	Current	no data	Others	Medium	https://climatepolicyinitiative.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/Land-Use-Finance-Tool.pdf	

47	MicroLEIS DSS	MicroLEIS DSS - (Mediterranean Land Evaluation Information System) is a set of useful tools for decision-making which in a wide range of agro-ecological schemes	https://microleis.evenor-tech.com/brain/	Operational	Evenor-Tech	Academy/Research Center	1998	Spain	Analysis	Agriculture	Agricultural/Forestry Decision Support Systems	yes	Regional and local	Both	Dataset	Aggregated data	Current	no data	Land managers	Medium	de La Rosa, D., Mayol, F., Diaz-Pereira, E., Fernandez, M., & de La Rosa, D. (2004). A land evaluation decision support system (MicroLEIS DSS) for agricultural soil protection: With special reference to the Mediterranean region. Environmental Modelling & Software, 19(10), 929-942. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envs.oft.2003.10.006
48	Myforest	myForest provides comprehensive online mapping, digital tools and the latest resources not only to sustainably manage forests, but to provide unique support for the creation of new forests around Britain.	https://myforest.sylvia.org.uk/	Operational	Rich Pigott, Ollie Price, Gwyneth Bradbury, Paul Orsi, Andrew Clark, Gabriel Hemery	Other	2023	United Kingdom	Interaction and visualization	Forestry	Forest Management	yes	National, regional and local	Both	Spatial information	Aggregated data	Current	no data	Land managers	Medium	Not available